

Role of reductant and photosensitizer in solar energy conversion and storage : ascorbic acid-eosin system

K. M. Gangotri and R. C. Meena*

Department of Chemistry, Jai Narain Vyas University, Jodhpur-324 005, India

E-mail : rcmeena007@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 17 April 2001, revised 2 September 2003, accepted 18 February 2004

Photogalvanic effects was studied in photogalvanic cell containing ascorbic acid as reductant and eosin as photosensitizer. The photopotential and photocurrent generated were 860.0 mV and 90.0 μ A, respectively. The observed conversion efficiency was 0.4474% and the maximum power of cell was 46.5 μ W. The storage capacity of the cell as 36.0 min in dark. The effect of different parameters on electrical output of the cell was observed and a mechanism has also been proposed for the generation of photocurrent in photogalvanic cells.

The photogeneration of electricity has attracted attention of scientists as viable media for solar energy conversion with bright future prospects.

Becquerel¹ first observed in 1839 the flow of current between two unsymmetrical illuminated metal electrodes in sunlight. The photogalvanic effect was first of all reported by Rideal and Williams² but it was systematically investigated by Rabinowitch³. Later on Kaneka and Yamada⁴, Murthy *et al.*⁵, Rohtagi-Mukherjee *et al.*⁶, Ameta *et al.*⁷ and Gangotri *et al.*⁸ have reported some interesting photogalvanic systems. Gangotri and Meena⁹ have studied the role of reductants in photogalvanic cells. Janu¹⁰ studied the comparison of different photogalvanic cells. Theretical conversion efficiency of photogalvanic cell is about 18% but the observed conversion efficiencies are quite low due to low stability of dyes, back electron transfer, aggregation of dye molecules around electrodes etc. Hoffman and Lichtin¹¹ have discussed various problems encountered in the development of this field.

In continuation of our work on different photosensitizers and reductants in photogalvanic cells, we report here our results in the use of the ascorbic acid-eosin system in the photogalvanic cell for solar energy conversion and storage.

Results and discussion

Effect of variation of pH :

The electrical out put of the cell was affected by the variation in pH of the system (Table 1) with a maximum at pH 12.7 and further increase in pH, there was a decrease in photopotential and photocurrent. Thus, photogalvanic cells

containing the ascorbic acid-eosin system were found to be quite sensitive to the pH of the solutions.

Table 1. Effect of variation of pH

[Eosin] = 2.40×10^{-5} M, [ascorbic acid] = 6.00×10^{-3} M,
Temp. = 303 K, light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}

	pH				
	10.8	12.2	12.7	13.2	13.8
Photopotential (mV)	828.0	842.0	860.0	847.0	821.0
Photocurrent (μ A)	53.0	74.0	90.0	79.0	57.0
Power (μ W)	43.8	62.3	77.4	66.9	46.7

It was observed that the pH for the optimum condition has relation with pK_a of the reductant and the desired pH is higher than its pK_a value ($\text{pH} > pK_a$). The reason may be the availability of reductant in its anionic form, which is a better donor form.

Effect of variation of ascorbic acid concentration :

The electrical output of the cell was affected by the variation of reducing agent concentration (ascorbic acid) in the system, the results are summarized in Table 2. Lower concentration of reducing agents results into a fall in electrical output because fewer reducing agent molecules were available for electron donation by dye molecules.

Table 2. Effect of variation of [ascorbic acid] concentration

[Eosin] = 2.40×10^{-5} M, light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} ,
pH = 12.7, Temp. = 303 K

	Ascorbic acid 10^3 M				
	5.00	5.50	6.00	6.50	7.20
Photopotential (mV)	832.0	848.0	860.0	852.0	826.0
Photocurrent (μ A)	54.0	78.0	90.0	82.0	69.0
Power (μ W)	44.9	66.1	77.4	69.8	56.9

Large concentration of reducing agent again resulted into a decrease in electrical output, because the large number of reducing agent molecules hinder the dye molecules reaching the electrode in the desired time limit.

Effect of variation of eosin concentration :

Dependence of electrical output on the concentration of dye was studied and the results are summarized in Table 3.

Lower concentration of dye resulted into a fall in photopotential and photocurrent because fewer dye molecules are available for the excitation and consecutive donation of the electrons to the platinum electrode. The greater concentration of dye again resulted into a decrease in electrical output as the intensity of light reaching the dye molecule near the electrode decreases due to absorption of the major portion of the light by dye molecules present in path.

Table 3. Effect of variation of [eosin] concentration

[Ascorbic acid] = $6.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} , pH = 12.7, Temp. = 303 K

	Eosin $10^5 M$				
	1.7	2.0	2.4	2.8	3.0
Photopotential (mV)	833.0	848.0	860.0	853.0	838.0
Photocurrent (μA)	53.0	75.0	90.0	80.0	62.0
Power (μW)	44.1	63.6	77.4	68.2	51.9

Effect of diffusion length :

The effect of variation of diffusion length (distance between the two electrodes) on the current parameters of the cell was studied using H-cells of different dimension. The results are reported in Table 4.

It was observed that there was sharp increase in photocurrent i_{max} in the first few minutes of illumination and then there was a gradual decrease to a stable value of photocurrent. This photocurrent at equilibrium is represented as i_{eq} . This kind of photocurrent behaviour is an initial rapid action followed by a slow rate determining step at a later stage.

On the basis of the effect of diffusion path length on the current parameters as investigated by Kaneko and Yamada⁴ it may be concluded that the leuco or semi reduced form of dye and the dye itself are the main electroactive species at the illuminated and the dark electrodes, respectively. However, the reducing agents and its oxidized products behave as the electron carries in the cell diffusing through the path.

Table 4. Effect of diffusion length

[Eosin] = $2.40 \times 10^{-5} M$, [ascorbic acid] = $6.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH = 12.7, Temp. = 303 K, light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}

DL (mm)	i_{max} (μA)	i_{eq} (μA)	Rate of initial generation of current $\mu A \text{ min}^{-1}$
35.0	142.0	92.0	12.2
40.0	147.0	93.0	13.4
45.0	150.0	90.0	15.0
50.0	154.0	90.0	16.2
55.0	158.0	87.0	17.3

Current-voltage (i-V) characteristics and conversion efficiency :

It was observed that i-V curve of the cell deviated from its regular rectangular shape is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. i-V characteristics of ascorbic acid-eosin system.

A point on the i-V curve called the power point (PP) was determined where the product of potential and current was maximum. The value of potential and current at the power point are represented as V_{pp} and i_{pp} , respectively. With the help of i-V curve the fill factor and the conversion efficiency of cell were determined as 0.50 and 0.4474% respectively.

Cell performance :

The performance of the cell was studied by applying the external load necessary to maintain current and potential at the power point after removing the source of light until the output (power) to its half value at the power point in the dark. It was observed that the cell can be used in the dark at its power point for 36.0 min.

Electroactive species :

Various probable processes may be considered for the photocurrent generation in photogalvanic cells. The results of the effect of diffusion length on current parameters were utilized to know more about the electroactive species.

The oxidized form of the reductant is formed only in the illuminated chamber and if it is considered to be the elec-

troactive species in the dark chamber then it must diffuse from the illuminated chamber to the dark chamber to accept an electron from the electrode. As a consequence, the maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) and rate of increase in photocurrent should decrease with an increase in diffusion length, but this was not observed experimentally. The value (i_{eq}) was also observed to be independent with respect to change in diffusion length (rather it decrease slightly). Therefore, it may be concluded that the main electroactive species are the leuco or semi-leuco and the dye eosin in illuminated chamber and dark chamber respectively. However, the reductant and its oxidized products act only as electron carrier in the path.

Mechanism :

On the basis of the above investigations the mechanism of the photocurrent generation in the photogalvanic cell can be proposed as follows :

Illuminated chamber :

Bulk solution :

At electrode :

Dark chamber :

At electrode :

Bulk solution :

where D, D⁻, R and R⁺ are the eosin and its semi or leuco forms, reductants and its oxidized form respectively.

Experimental

Ascorbic acid (LOBA), eosin (Qualigens) and sodium hydroxide (s.d. fine) were used. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water and stored in amber coloured containers. A mixture of solutions of ascorbic acid, eosin and sodium hydroxide was taken in an H-type glass tube. A platinum electrode (1.0 × 1.0 cm²) was immersed into its one arm and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) in the other.

It was placed in dark till a stable potential was obtained. Then the arm containing the SCE was kept in the dark and the platinum electrode was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp. A water-filter was used to cut off IR radiations. The photochemical bleaching of eosin was studied potentiometrically. A Agronic 511 pH meter and a OSAW (India) micrometer were used to measure the potential and current generated by the system, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Head of the Department of Chemistry, Jai Narain Vyas University, Jodhpur for facilities. Thanks are also due to Mr. Pooran Koli, Department of Chemistry for his critical discussions and to Mr. Shankar Lal Meena for interpretation of observations. The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. K. Bacquerel, *C. R. Acad. Sci., Paris*, 1839, **9**, 14; 1839, **9**, 561.
2. E. K. Rideal and D. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 258.
3. E. Rabinowitch, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1940, **8**, 551; 1940, **8**, 560.
4. Kaneko and A. Yamada, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, **8**, 1213.
5. A. S. N. Murthy, H. C. Dak and K. S. Reddy, *Int. J. Energy Res.*, 1980, **4**, 339.
6. K. K. Rohtagi-Mukherjee, M. Roy and B. B. Bhowmik, *Solar Energy*, 1983, **31**, 417.
7. S. C. Ameta, P. K. Jain, A. K. Janu and R. Ameta, *The Energy Journal (U.K.)*, 1985, **58**, 8; S. C. Ameta, S. Khamesra, S. Lodha and R. Ameta, *J. Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1989, **48**, 8; S. C. Ameta, A. K. Chittora, K. M. Gangotri and S. Khamesra, *Z. Phy. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1989, **270**, 607.
8. K. M. Gangotri, P. Kalla, K. R. Genwa, Chhaganlal, O. P. Regar and R. Meena, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 1994, **2**, 19; K. M. Gangotri, O. P. Regar, Chhaganlal, P. Kalla, K. R. Genwa and R. Meena, *Int. J. Energy Res.*, 1996, **20**, 581; *Arab. J. Sc. Engg.*, 1997, **22**, 115.
9. K. M. Gangotri, R. C. Meena and R. Meena, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1999, **123**, 93; K. M. Gangotri and R. C. Meena, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2001, **141**, 175.
10. A. K. Janu, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2000, **132**, 1.
11. M. Z. Hoffman and N. N. Lichtin, "Solar Energy", eds. R. R. Hantala, R. B. King and C. Kotal Clifton, N. J. Publisher, 153.